

ANTI-G SUIT PRESSURE - HOW MUCH IS JUST RIGHT?

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ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the early development of anti-G suits and G-valves as well as contemporary research on advanced anti-G protection systems. The classic works of Dr Earl Wood, Dr George Hallenbeck, and others in the 1940s resulted in the basic G-suit and inflation schedules still in use in the USAF. The standard mechanical G-valve senses the Gz level and regulates G-suit pressure in at a linear rate of 1.5 psi/Gz. Currently, numerous anti-G valves utilizing modern control techniques are under development. Microprocessors are being advocated to monitor the aircraft status and thereby control the G-suit inflation. It is possible that additional inputs such as onset rate, anticipated peak Gz, seat back angle, time at G, individual variability, comfort, and the pilot's physiologic status should also be considered in determining the optimum G-suit inflation parameters. A non-linear G-suit inflation rate, pre-inflation, sequential or pulsating pressure schedules could also be utilized by new concept valves and may be techniques to provide improved protection to the pilot against G-induced loss of consciousness.

INTRODUCTION: The objective of this paper is to present a brief overview of the development of anti-G protection systems and to identify some current research efforts and issues pertaining to improving the protection and performance of pilots in high acceleration environments. It is not possible for this review to be an all inclusive coverage of acceleration research, but rather present typical developments.

The pilots of aircraft performing maneuvers such as loops, tight turns, and pull-outs are subjected to increased gravitational force with the inertial force acting from head to foot (+Gz). The cardiovascular system is very sensitive to increased Gz. If sufficient head-level blood pressure and blood flow are not maintained, the pilot will experience symptoms ranging from loss of vision to unconsciousness. As early as 1924, Doolittle (7) described the reduced visual phenomenon that occurred in flight during sustained maneuvers exceeding 4.5 Gz. In 1933, Poppen (18) obtained direct blood pressure recordings from a dog strapped in the rear cockpit of a BM-2 aircraft. He also devised a pneumatically

inflatable abdominal belt that, when inflated to 1.5 psi 30 seconds before the maneuver, produced a "marked improvement in the physiological changes" during 4 Gz turns. The first human centrifuge in the United States was constructed in 1937 at Wright Field, Dayton, OH under the direction of Dr Harry Armstrong. World War II gave great impetus to acceleration research and the development of anti-G suits and valves. Tables I and II contain information taken from the 1946 report by Hallenbeck (11) that summarized much of the research conducted during that era.

The Franks Flying Suit (FFS) utilized a lower body water filled suit to provide counter pressure against the footward fluid shift caused by Gz. Although successfully demonstrated in flight to reduce fatigue and improve Gz tolerance, it was not accepted by the pilots because of weight, bulk, warmth, and restriction of movement. The Arterial Occlusion Suit (AOS) used high pressures at the thighs and upper arms to limit blood flow to the limbs, thereby increasing central blood volume and flow. Pilots rejected the suit because it was too uncomfortable. The G-1 suit consisted of 17 bladders inflated with 3 different pressures. About 500 of the suits were in service during World War II. The suit's many defects included weight (10 lbs), restriction of movement, heat retention, and unnecessary complexity. A modified version, (the G-2) used just 5 bladders, a single pressure, and reduced the weight to 4.5 lbs. Over 3000 G-2 suits were in service in Europe during World War II. The G-3 was a 5 bladder cut-a-way suit designed to be worn over the pilot's flight clothing. It was standardized in 1944, with over 4000 suits being issued during World War II. This suit received the best degree of pilot acceptance. The current USAF suit, the CSU-13B/P, is basically an improved G-3 suit. The G-4 was a coverall garment incorporating the 5 bladders of the G-3 into a flight suit.

Physiological Effects and Gz Tolerance

The classic works of Dr Earl Wood (21,22) and others have documented the decrease in head-level arterial blood pressure and blood flow that occurs during increased Gz exposures. Blood pooling in the lower body can reduce venous return to the heart and hence reduce cardiac output. The typical symptoms experienced by a subject at increased Gz levels progress from

peripheral light loss (PLL) to blackout (BO) to loss of consciousness (LOC). At high onset rates to high Gz levels, however, the subject may not experience the warning of PLL before G-induced loss of consciousness (G-LOC) occurs. The average blackout level for a relaxed, unprotected subject is about 3.5 to 4.0 Gz with unconsciousness occurring about 1 G higher. Head level blood pressure is reduced by about 22 mm Hg for each 1 Gz increase; hence the average, relaxed individual has a head-level blood pressure of zero at about 5 Gz. Pilots of highly maneuverable aircraft are routinely exposed to acceleration levels of over 5 Gz with some exposures as high as 9 Gz. At these high levels the pilot is dependent upon the G-suit in combination with a properly executed straining maneuver (M-1 or L-1) to maintain vision, consciousness, and control of the aircraft. A 1984 survey by Pluta (17) revealed that 227 of 1903 (12%) USAF Tactical Air Force aircrew had recalled at least one in-flight episode of G-LOC. While respondents in Pluta's study reported the greatest number of G-LOC episodes in the F-15, F-4, and F-16 there were some incidents reported in the less agile F-106, F-100, and F-111 as well. The first recorded incident of G-LOC occurred during World War I (1916-18). Once G-LOC occurs, the aircrewman is incapacitated an average of 31 seconds, but extending as long as one minute in some individuals. Between 1983 and mid-1985, seven USAF class A mishaps resulting in the loss of five F-16, one F-5 one A-10 aircraft and their crewmembers have been officially attributed to G-LOC (3). Individual differences, physical conditioning, acclimation, daily variations, onset rate, duration, and seat back angle are some other factors affecting Gz tolerance. Select USAF pilots have been receiving high-G centrifuge training that includes a review of high-G physiology, the demonstration of an effective anti-G straining maneuver, and a series of centrifuge rides up to 9 Gz (9).

Anti-G Suits and Their Function:

Anti-G suits are garments that encircle the lower extremities and contain pneumatic bladders. The currently deployed USAF model CSU-13 B/P anti-G suit contains 5 interconnected bladders, one each overlying the abdomen and each thigh and calf. Inflation of the suit is accomplished by an inertially activated mechanical valve through an umbilical hose to the abdominal bladder. When inflated, the anti-G suit compresses the abdomen and lower extremities. Studies of the effect of anti-G suit inflation on man reveal several reasons for their +Gz tolerance enhancing effects. Using dye dilution techniques, Gray et al. (10) demonstrated significant cardiovascular changes resulting from G-suit inflation in subjects both supine and at 60 degrees passive head-up tilt. Inflation augmented venous return with the shifting of blood from the periphery to the central circulation, thereby increasing central blood volume, central venous pressure, mean

arterial blood pressure, and cardiac index. This increase in cardiac index was transient, however, declining in the head-up subjects from 153% of baseline at suit inflation to 128% of baseline after 45 seconds. Jennings et al. (15) studied the effect on cardiac volumes determined by echocardiography during G-suit inflation while subjects were exposed to 3.0 Gz for 30 seconds. Their results indicated that, upon G-suit inflation while under +Gz stress, cardiac output increased to approximately 125% of baseline but decreased significantly over the ensuing 30 seconds. They postulated that a G-suit that periodically deflated and inflated might keep the suit functioning more effectively. Given this transient but critical function in increasing venous return it is intuitive that, for optimum benefit, an anti-G suit should inflate the calf bladders first and progress toward the heart. However, Begin (2) reported that inflation pressures in the CSU-12 B/P anti-G suit (predecessor of but similar to the CSU-13 B/P suit) at any time during filling were greatest in the abdominal bladder, followed by the calf bladders, and lastly the thigh bladders. This retrograde inflation could potentially sequester blood in the lower extremities rather than return it to the central circulation. The anti-G suit is noted to increase arterial blood pressure, augment the M-1/L-1 straining maneuvers, elevate the heart so as to reduce the heart-to-eye distance, increase peripheral resistance, and improve venous return.

There is renewed interest in new G-suit designs that sequentially inflate from foot toward abdomen or that cover more surface area. Although several other methods of increasing G tolerance are recognized (i.e., body positioning, positive pressure breathing, strength training, etc.), the studies reported in Table II and III are limited to those that used a conventional upright seat (+Gz) and a five bladder anti-G suit.

Discussion & Recommendations

Some research efforts are concerned with monitoring the status of the pilot and intervening with the aircraft's flight path to avert a ground impact in the event of G-LOC (12). Other efforts are directed toward improving the G-protection system. Improvements of G-tolerance over the standard valve have been reported by various researchers (Table III) by improving the valve responsiveness, using higher initial or overall pressure, or using pulsating pressure.

New electronic G-valves are under development in order to improve the efficiency of the G-suit. The major focus of these new valves has been to improve the responsiveness of the valve to provide timely inflation of the G-suit during rapidly changing Gz maneuvers (16, 19). Perhaps a more generic and equally important consideration should be to define the optimum G-suit pressure for various Gz levels and conditions. For many years, the mechanical G-valve has been designed to open at about 1.5 Gz and to provide a

linear pressure output of 1.5 psi/G. This system is simple, reliable, economical, and provides the pilot with a good protection system. The new electronic microprocessor-controlled valves have the potential of inflating the G-suit in radically different ways. It is possible that a better G protection system would utilize a non-linear output, variable opening point, and if conditions warrant it higher and/or pulsating pressure. Inputs to such a system may include the Gz level, onset rate, anticipated peak G, time at G, recent G time history, and the pilot's physiological status. A microprocessor-controlled system could also be tailored for the individual pilot as well as the aircraft and its flight status and mission.

The optimum G-suit pressure may depend upon many factors beyond the presently used Gz level. Assuming the near term G-protection system will require protecting the pilot in an upright seat and wearing a conventional five bladder anti-G suit, a microprocessor-controlled G-valve could be designed with the following considerations: Responsiveness - to utilize high flow rate (i.e., ≥ 30 SCFM) and accurate pressure feedback to eliminate the lag inherent in present mechanical valves.

Opening Point - to remain closed during buffet or transients but to open during sustained G (i.e., ≥ 1.25 Gz) with sufficient flow at low Gz to provide timely G-suit inflation.

Anti-G Suit Pressure: High pressure and comfort are inversely related (13). Pilot acceptance and ultimate performance enhancement and protection may be achieved by the non-linear type G/PSI schedule presented in Figure 2. In zone I (1.25 to 3.0 Gz) G-LOC is highly unlikely and G-suit pressure could be reduced from that required by the present MIL-SPEC (8). Accordingly, G-suit pressure could be increased in zones III (5-7 Gz) and IV (7-10 Gz) where loss of vision and G-LOC are most likely to occur.

Time at G - During sustained rapid onset acceleration studies conducted on centrifuges, the time for PLL, BO, or G-LOC most likely to occur for relaxed subjects is from 4 to 10 sec after reaching the plateau. During this time, the tissue oxygen reserves have been depleted but the reflex cardiovascular compensation has yet to fully occur. Furthermore, because of the reflex cardiac compensation, most relaxed subjects who tolerate the first 10 sec of a G epoch are then able to sustain that G level for an additional 20 sec or longer without further symptoms (1). Perhaps an advanced G-valve should be programmed to utilize these physiological factors. In zone I for example, G-suit pressure could be reduced by 50% after 15 sec of sustained exposure. In zone II suit pressure reductions of 50% at 3 G to no reduction at 5 G is suggested. In zones III & IV higher pressure and possibly pressure pulsations (i.e., + 1 psi - 2 psi every 4 sec) may aid the pilots in the performance of the M-1 straining maneuver as well as increase venous return.

The potential of new anti-G valves and the increased capabilities of modern fighter aircraft warrant a reexamination of the specification of the optimum G-suit pressure. How much G-suit pressure is just right? This report does not have the answer to this question. Research utilizing various G-suit inflation techniques, objective physiological measures, visual symptoms, and subjective comfort criteria could identify an improved G-protection system.

REFERENCES

1. Albery WB, Van Patten RE, Gordon TA, Frazier JW, Goodyear C. Human tolerance enhancement in high onset rate, high sustained +Gz with a pulsating servo anti-G valve. *SAFE Journal*. 1987;17:1; 24-31.
2. Begin R, Dougherty R, Michaelson E, Sackner MA. Effect of sequential anti-g suit inflation on pulmonary capillary blood flow in man. *Aviat. Space Environ. Med.* 1976; 47:937-41.
3. Burton RR. G-induced loss of consciousness: definition, history, current status. *Aviat. Space Environ. Med.* 1988; 59:2-5.
4. Burton RR, Parkhurst MJ, Leverett SD. +Gz protection afforded by standard and preacceleration inflation of the bladder and capstan type G-suits. *Aviat. Space Environ. Med.* 1973; 44:488-94.
5. Burton RR, Shaffstall RM, Jaggars JL. Development, test, and evaluation of an advanced anti-G valve for the F-15. *Aviat. Space Environ. Med.* 1980; 51:504-9.
6. Crosbie RJ. A servo controlled rapid response anti-G valve. NADC-83087-60. Naval Air Development Center, Warminster, PA. Oct 1983.
7. Doolittle JH. Accelerations in flight. Tenth Annual Report of National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics. TR-203. 1924.
8. Frazier JW, Ratino DA, Goodyear CD, Gould LH, Gruesbeck WC. Initial centrifuge tests of a subject controllable anti-g valve. *SAFE Journal*. 1987; 17:2;38-44.
9. Gillingham KK, Fosdick JP. High-g training for fighter aircrew. *Aviat. Space Environ. Med.* 1988; 59:12-19.
10. Gray S, Shaver JA, Kroetz FW, Leonard JJ. Acute and prolonged effects of g-suit inflation on cardiovascular dynamics. *J. Aviat. Med.* 1969; 40:40-3.
11. Hallenbeck GA. Design and use of anti-G suits and their activating valves in world war II. Army Air Force Technical Report 5433. Wright Field, Dayton, OH. Mar 1946.

12. Howard JD, Johnston AM. AFTI/F-16 gravity-induced loss-of-consciousness and spatial disorientation auto-recovery system. Proceeding of IEEE/NAECON. May 1986; 752-58.

13. Hrebien L, Hendler E. Factors affecting human tolerance to sustained acceleration. Aviat. Space Environ. Med. 1985; 56:19-26.

14. Jaron D, Moore TW, Reddy BRS, Kepics F, Hrebien L. Increased acceleration tolerance using a pulsating anti-G suit. Proceedings of IEEE/NAECON. May 1987; 1011-13.

15. Jennings TJ, Seaworth J, Ratino D, Tripp L, Howell L, Goodyear, C. The effect of +Gz acceleration on cardiac volumes determined by two-dimensional echocardiography. SAFE Journal 1985; 15:4; 4-9.

16. Meeker LJ, Krueger AG, Love P. An engineering test and evaluation of the French EROS, Moog-Carleton, and Garrett fluidic anti-g valves. 25th Annual SAFE Symposium. Nov 1987.

17. Pluta JC. LOC survey. Flying Safety. 1984; 25-8.

18. Poppen JR, Drinker CK. Physiological effects and possible methods of reducing the symptoms produced by rapid changes in speed and direction of airplanes as measured in actual flight. J. Appl. Physiol. 1950; 3:204-216.

19. Ratajczak M. Anti-g valves: when is fast, too fast? 25th Annual SAFE Symposium. Nov 1987.

20. Van Patten RE, Jennings TJ, Albery W, Frazier JW, Goodyear C. Development of an electro-pneumatic anti-g valve for high performance fighter aircraft. 22nd Annual SAFE Symposium. Dec 1984; 112-6.

21. Wood EH, Lambert EH. Some factors which influence the protection afforded by pneumatic anti-g suits. J. Aviat. Med. 1952; 23:218-228.

22. Wood EH, Lambert EH, Code CF. The hydro-and resulting bio-dynamics of +Gz induced loss of consciousness and its history. Proceeding of IEEE/NAECON. May 1987; 988-95.

Figure 1. The current military specification (MIL-V-87223) for anti-g suit pressure is in the shaded area and various other PSI/G and opening points as reported by Hallenbeck and others.

TABLE I. DATA FROM HALLENBECK OF NONCONVENTIONAL ANTI-G SUITS

Anti-G Suit	Remarks	Average Visual Protection (Gz)
Gradient Pressure Suit (G-1)	Three pressures	1.3 - 1.5
Franks Flying Suit (FFS)	Water filled	0.9 - 2.1
Pneumatic Lever Suit (PLS)	Pneumatic capstan	1.2 - 1.6
Arterial Occlusion Suit (AOS)	High pressure	2.6

TABLE II. DATA FROM HALLENBECK OF CONVENTIONAL FIVE BLADDER & SINGLE PRESSURE ANTI-G SUITS

<u>PSI/G</u>	<u>Opening Point (Gz)</u>	<u>Protection (Gz)</u>	<u>Anti-G Suit</u>
1.0	1.0	1.4	G-2
1.25	1.0	1.4	G-2
1.0	1.0	1.1	G-3
1.0	1.5	0.8	G-3
0.86	1.0	1.0	G-4
1.0	1.5	1.1	G-4
1.0	1.0	1.4	G-4
1.0	1.75	1.3	G-4
1.0	1.75	1.2	Z-2
1.5	1.75	1.6	Z-2

TABLE III. REPORTED IMPROVEMENTS OVER THE STANDARD ANTI-G SUIT AND VALVE

<u>Gz Improvement</u>	<u>Condition</u>	<u>Reference</u>
0.40	Pulsating Pressure (± 2.0 psi)	14
0.41	Pre-inflation to 1.0 psi	4
1.0	High Flow-Ready Pressure (HFRP)	5
0.46	Servo Rapid Response Valve	6
1.32	Servo Rapid Response Valve	6
0.45	Higher pressure (1.88 psi/G-1)	13
1.06	Bang-Bang Servo Valve (BBSV)	20
1.37*	BBSV - Higher pressure & 4 Sec pulsations	1

* Versus the High Flow Only (HFO) Valve.

Figure 2. A recommended non-linear pressure schedule with four G_z zones as compared with the standard MIL-SPEC (shaded area).

Figure 3. The G-3A anti-G suit is very similar to the current CSU-13B/P. The G-5A used the pneumatic lever principle. Circa 1946.

Figure 4. Various historic anti-G suits. Left to right are the Franks Flying Suit (Milt Alexander), Gradient Pressure Suit G-1 (Dr Sidney Leverett), Arterial Occlusion Suit (Lt GII Johnson), G-3A (Frank Saul), MB-2 Coverall (John Frazier), CSU-3/P (SSgt George Sutton), and the Bikini (Ray Whitney). Circa 1957.